

‘SHAstra DHARA’ VIS-À-VIS SURGICAL OUTCOMES***¹Dr. Sakshi Bisht, ²Dr. Ajay Kumar Gupta**

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ABSTRACT

“Surgery is not just cutting, but it is an art; it is not only an art but also a merciful art.”

-Anonymous

Ayurveda is the ancient science of Indian system of medicine. It comprises of two words, *Ayu-* meaning ‘life’, and *Veda-* meaning ‘knowledge’ or ‘science’. *Shalya Tantra*, the surgical branch of *Ayurveda*, is one of the most advanced disciplines described in classical *Ayurvedic* literature. Among its fundamental operative principles, *Shastra Dhara*, the maintenance and proper sharpness of surgical instruments, holds prime importance. *Acharya Sushruta* is renowned as the ‘Father of Surgery’ worldwide. His brilliance is unmatched and well accepted even today. The surgical instruments used in modern era are all a contribution and modification of the surgical instruments mentioned by *Acharya Sushruta*. The

description in *Sushruta Samhita* is elaborate and minutely detailed, so much so that *Acharya Sushruta* not only explains the various types of surgical instruments, their handling and application but also emphasizes on the importance of *Shastra Dhara*. Irrespective of classical *Ayurvedic* surgeries or modern-day surgeries, the efficiency of an operative procedure largely depends upon the quality and maintenance of the surgical instruments, especially their *Dhara* (cutting edge). The courageous heart and skilled hands of a *Shalya Chikitsak* require the precise instruments for the success of *Shalya Karma*.

KEYWORDS: *Shastra Dhara, Shalya Tantra, Shastra Payana*, surgical instruments.

INTRODUCTION

Shalya Tantra is regarded as the surgical specialty of *Ayurveda*, systematically codified in the *Sushruta Samhita*. *Acharya Sushruta* described surgical instruments, operative techniques, wound management, and post-operative care in a detailed and scientific manner. Among these, the concept of *Shastra Dhara* occupies a central position.

- *Shastra* = surgical instruments (sharp tools)
- *Dhara* = sharpness/edge

Shastra Dhara, therefore refers to the quality, sharpening, maintenance and correct use of sharp surgical instruments, which is a key aspect in classical surgical practice. It implies instruments that are well-sharpened, balanced, and capable of producing clean, precise incisions.

Acharya Sushruta has broadly classified various surgical instruments as.

1. *YANTRA* (Blunt instruments)
2. *SHAstra* (Sharp instruments)

All sharp surgical instruments are collectively referred to as *Shastra*, and therefore special emphasis is placed on their *Dhara* (cutting edge), including its significance and proper maintenance. *Sushruta Samhita* describes twenty distinct types of *Shastra* (sharp surgical instruments).^[1]

Acharya Sushruta explains the qualities (*Guṇa*) and defects (*Doṣha*) of both *Yantra* (blunt instruments) and *Shastra* (sharp instruments).

While mentioning the *guna* (qualities/characteristics) of *Shastra*, he deliberately uses the term “*Sudharani*.” - meaning the ideal *Shastra* should have a sharp cutting edge.^[2]

The emphasis is not only on the type of instrument but also on its.

- Sharpness
- Material quality
- Size and proportion
- Ease of handling
- Proper storage and sterilization

QUALITIES OF A SURGEON^[3]

Acharya Sushruta has described qualities of a *Shalya Chikitsak* (surgeon), while performing *Shashtra Karma* (surgical procedure), viz.

- 1) *Shauryam* – Courage and Fearlessness.
- 2) *Ashukriya* – Quick action or promptness in performing surgeries as well as decision making ability.
- 3) *Shashtra-taikshnyam* – Sharpness and availability of required surgical instruments.
- 4) *Asweda* – Minimal-to-no perspiration, which signifies no nervousness.
- 5) *Avepathu*- Absence of tremors in hands, signifying precision in instrument handling, so as not to traumatize the adjacent structures.
- 6) *Asammoh* – Absence of confusion or dilemma, with a fully conscious state of body and mind.

In *Shalya Tantra*, the qualities of a surgeon, as well as the availability of appropriate surgical instruments, both are equally important, in deciding the success rate of any surgical procedure. The *Shalya Chikitsak* is expected to examine all the required instruments before surgery. Thus, *Shashtra Dhara* symbolizes not just the instrument's edge, but also the sharpness of the surgeon's intellect and training.

Hence, the term *SHASTRA DHARA* reflects not merely the physical sharpness of surgical instruments but also the precision, skill, and discipline required by the surgeon in performing surgical procedures.

TYPES OF SHASTRA DHARA

In any surgical procedure, the initial step typically involves making an incision on the patient, however, this is soon followed by several additional steps necessary to complete the operation. Therefore, *Acharya Sushruta* describes eight types *Shashtra karma*.^[4]

There are different types of *Shashtra Dhara* designated for various *Shashtra Karma* procedures.^[5]

<i>SHASTRA DHARA</i>	<i>SHASTRA KARMA</i>
<i>Maasoori</i>	<i>Bhedana</i>
<i>Ardha-maasoori</i>	<i>Lekhana</i>
<i>Kaishiki</i>	<i>Vyadhana, Visravana</i>
<i>Ardha-kaishiki</i>	<i>Chhedana</i>

SHAstra PAYANA

The continuous use of sharp surgical instruments can lead to wearing off the sharpness, with time. This occurs due to mechanical wear, microscopic corrosion, micro-chipping and edge-deformation. Every time a blade cuts tissue, sutures or other material, microscopic friction occurs. Repeated contact with dense tissues can accelerate blunting of the instrument. Even slight deformation reduces cutting efficiency. Hence, it is crucial to pay heed in the maintenance of the sharpness and efficacy of the surgical instruments.

Even in contemporary surgical practice, sharp instruments are generally not subjected to autoclaving.^[6] Because the high heat and pressure in an autoclave can damage the sharpness of the instruments, rendering them useless for next use. Rather the sharp instruments are kept dipped in 2% Glutaraldehyde or Lysol solution for disinfection.^[7]

The concept of disposable blades is also focused for maintaining optimal cutting efficiency. The advent of disposable blades in the late 1920's transformed surgical practice. These blades could be mass-produced in multiple shapes and sizes and were conveniently replaced as soon as they became dull, according to the surgeon's preference. Moreover, carbon steel blades offer greater sharpness compared to stainless steel, and concerns about their tendency to rust are insignificant, as they are discarded and incinerated well before any corrosion can occur.^[8]

Acharya Sushruta recognized this principle and therefore described the concept of *Shastra Payana*, which refers to the tempering of sharp instruments. *Payana* is a process where sharp instruments are heated to core and extinguished in liquid medium, to cool down and this process is repeated as per need, to maintain their blade acuity. There are 3 types of *Shastra Payana* viz., *Kshar (Alkali)*, *Udaka (Water)*, *Taila (oil)*.^[9]

SHAstra PAYANA	PRAYOGA
<i>Kshar Payit Shastra</i>	<i>Shar Shalya Asthi Chhedana</i>
<i>Udaka Payit Shastra</i>	<i>Mansa Chhedana Bhedana Patana</i>
<i>Taila Payit Shastra</i>	<i>Sira Vyadhana, Snayu Chhedana</i>

In addition to this, to re-establish and maintain the sharpness of the surgical instruments, *Acharya Sushruta* also mentions the use of *Masha-varna Shlakshana Shila* and *Shalmali Phalaka*.^[10]

Masha-varna Shlakshana Shila refers to a smooth, fine-textured stone slab that is black in colour like black gram. These specifications indicate that the stone should be dense, hard and

uniform in structure, free from roughness or cracks, suitable for producing a fine sharp cutting edge.

SHALMALI^[11]

BOTANICAL NAME- *Bombax ceiba* Linn.

FAMILY- Bombacaceae

It is a deciduous tree, upto 30 m tall, with grey bark, covered with black, conical prickles and red bright vibrant flowers.

Shalmali Phalaka refers to a board or plank of *Shalmali* or Red Silk Cotton tree wood. After sharpening of the instrument, the edge should be refined by rubbing it on this plank of *Shalmali* wood. Not just for edge maintenance, it is also used for instrument storage and protection. Due to its soft and non-abrasive nature, the *Shalmali* wood is ideal for storing delicate, sharp surgical tools to prevent them from becoming blunt.

QUALITIES OF IDEAL SHASTRA DHARA^[12]

Classical texts describe ideal surgical instrument for use as: *Sunishit, Romashchhedi*. *Acharya Sushruta* mentions that when the instrument is capable to cut through the *Loma*, then it is considered to have attained an ideal *Dhara*.

IMPORTANCE OF SHASTRA DHARA IN SHALYA TANTRA

1. Precision in Incision

A well-maintained cutting edge ensures.

- Clean and smooth incisions
- Minimal tissue trauma
- Reduced pain and bleeding
- Better wound healing

In contrast, blunt instruments can lead to tissue damage resulting in lacerated, crushed, or contused wounds. They tend to compress and tear tissues rather than create clean cuts, producing irregular wound margins and potentially impairing the healing.^[13]

Acharya Sushruta defines the qualities of the *Vrana* or incisions made by the *Shalya Chikitsak*. It clearly states that the *Vrana* should have these 5 qualities – *Aayat, Vishal, Suvibhakta, Nirashraya* and *Prapta-Kaalkrit*.^[14]

The word *Suvibhakta* means “well-distributed or properly allocated” incision, made using a sharp instrument. A *Suvibhakta Vrana* would imply, a wound with clearly defined margins, well differentiated and causing minimal tissue trauma.

A wound is a break in the integrity of the skin or tissues often, which may be associated with disruption of the structure and function.^[15]

Surgical procedures demand that the surgeon create precise and clean incision on the patient's body. The wounds intentionally produced during surgery are ideally incised wounds.

Incised wounds are produced by sharp instruments such as knives, blades, etc. These wounds are characterized by well-defined, sharp margins and comparatively minimal contamination. Because of their clean-cut nature, they are best managed with primary suturing, which promotes optimal healing and results in a fine, cosmetically acceptable scar.^[13]

According to Rank and Wakefield Classification, such wounds are categorized as tidy wounds. **Tidy wounds** include clean incised injuries involving healthy tissue and are rarely associated with tissue loss.^[15]

Therefore, surgically created tidy incised wounds provide favourable conditions for wound healing and facilitate faster post-operative recovery. This underscores the critical importance of maintaining sharp surgical instruments to ensure clean incisions and successful operative outcomes. In accordance with the principle of tissue respect, surgeons aim to minimize tissue trauma by using sharp, efficient, and well-maintained instruments.

2. Prevention of Complications

Proper *Shastra Dhara* reduces.

- Excessive bleeding
- Tissue necrosis
- Risk of infection
- Post-operative complications

Sushruta emphasized that an improperly sharpened instrument is dangerous in the hands of a surgeon.

APPLICATION IN *SHALYA TANTRA* TODAY

The principle of *Shastra Dhara* remains relevant in all surgical practices, which are being performed today globally. Proper instrument maintenance ensures successful operative outcomes and aligns classical practice advocated by *Acharya Sushruta* with surgical ethics.

CONCLUSION

Shastra Dhara is a foundational concept in *Shalya Tantra* that highlights the importance of sharp, precise, and well-maintained surgical instruments. Rooted in the teachings of *Acharya Sushruta*, it reflects both technical excellence and surgical ethics. Even in the modern era, the principle of precision, cleanliness, and skill remains timeless, and determine surgical success. Thus, *Shastra Dhara* stands as a testimony to the scientific depth of ancient *Ayurvedic* surgical knowledge and its continued relevance in contemporary practice.

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